

PROBLEMS OF TEACHING ENGLISH SPEAKING AT SCHOOL

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Abstract. *This article is about problems of teaching English speaking at school. It reveals different kinds of problems which students come across in learning English.*

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All of people use language to express their feeling, ideas, opinions, and desires. By the language, people can communicate to each other. According to Brown language is a system of arbitrary conventionalized, vocal, written, or gestural symbols that enable members of a given community to communicate intelligibly with one another. It means that language is a communication. In other words, language is a kind of communication between people in community. It is a value of interpersonal contact exchanging information. Everyone uses language to communicate. When people want to speak or deliver information to another people, they cannot do it without language. It should be language is important to communicate in human being [1,156].

People can develop their knowledge with getting the information. Language is intimately tied to man's feeling and activity. It means that language is used to express our feeling in daily activities to get information. Everyone needs language to express their opinions, desires, emotion in every conversation activity or dialogue. On the other word, written language is used on the public information such as books, newspaper, magazine, research so on.

In teaching learning process, perhaps student face some problems to speak. It makes the students do not success on speaking. According to Ur there are some problems across in teaching speaking:

a. Inhibition. Unlike reading, writing, and listening activities, speaking requires some degree of real-time exposure to an audience. Learners are often inhibited about trying to say things in a foreign language in the classroom: worried about making mistakes, fearful or criticism or losing face, or simply shy or the attention that their speech attracts.

b. Nothing to say. Even if they are not inhibited, you often hear learner complain that they cannot think of anything to say, they have no motive to express themselves beyond the guilty feeling that they should be speaking.

c. Low or uneven participation. Only one participant can talk at a time if he or she is to be heard; and in a large group this means that each one will have only very little talking time. This problem is compounded by the tendency of some learners to dominate, while others speak very little or not at all.

d. Mother-tongue use. In classes where all, or a number of, the learners share the same mother tongue, they may tend to use it: because it is easier, because it feels unnatural to speak to one another in a foreign language, and because they feel less 'exposed' if they are speaking their mother tongue. If they are talking in small groups it can be quite difficult to get some classes particularly the less disciplined or motivated ones to keep to the target language.

According to Krashen S., teachers also need to know their roles in teaching speaking. They have specific roles at different stages, as follows [2,58]:

- a. The presenting stage; when the teachers introduce something new to be learned, the teachers play a role as informants.
- b. The practice stage; when the teachers allow the learners to work under their direction, the teachers have a role as conductors and monitors.
- c. The production stage; when the teachers give the learner opportunity to work on their own.

It can be concluded that there are three roles in teaching speaking. They are the presenting, the practice stage, and the production stage. In the presenting stage, the teacher tells about new material that will be learned. The teacher gives knowledge and the direction about material. In practice stage, the teachers control the students when they work under the teachers direction. The production stage, the teachers give the students task to do by their own.

Teachers role to get the students speak fluently. According to Harmer however, three have particular relevance if we are trying to get students to speak fluently:

Prompter, students sometimes get lost, cannot think of what to say next, or in some other way lose the fluency we expect of them. We can leave them to struggle out of such situations of their own, and indeed sometimes this may be the best option. Participant, teachers should be good animator when asking students to procedure language. Feedback provider, the vexed question of when and how to give feedback in speaking activities is answered by considering carefully the effect to possible different approach. The ability to speak confidently and authentically is an essential life skill and a very clear way of measuring your ability in a foreign language. The speaking skill is an anxiety-provoking skill. When individuals speak in the target language, they often experience a high level of anxiety and thus become more unwilling to take part in conversational activities.

Most of the time in language classrooms, students do not want to speak for a number of reasons, including the fear of making a mistake, the fear of their teachers, feeling embarrassed if their peers laugh at their mistakes, low self-esteem and confidence, a lack of vocabulary and fluency, setting unrealistic goals, such as being as good as a native speaker, negative self-perceptions of language competence, and teachers' negative demeanor and attitude.

Considering these reasons in language classrooms, teachers that want to lessen the negative factors and create an anxiety-free atmosphere when teaching use various activities, such as games and role playing, as well as pair and group work by adopting communicative teaching methods, such as collaborative learning and task-based language teaching. In modern language teaching approaches, teachers take on different roles, such as facilitator, adviser and participant in the classroom in order to facilitate language learning among the students and encourage them to communicate in the target language [3,98].

Communication can be defined as the process of transmitting information and common understanding from one person to another. The definition underscores the fact that unless a common understanding results from the exchange of information, there is no communication. In a basis of teaching any subject at school including foreign language, there are general didactic principles. Such principles are: scientific character, availability, presentation in teaching, an individual approach in conditions of collective work and others [2,134].

Specific and general didactic principles express typical, main, essential, that should characterize teaching a foreign language at school and, first of all at the beginning stage where bases of mastering are pawned by this subject. The understanding of action of principles of teaching and direct use of rules will allow the teacher to carry out teaching effectively.

Learning is the active process which is carried out through involving pupils in a various activities, thus making it active participant in reception of education. In this bilateral process it is possible to allocate the basic functions which are carried out by each the parts. The teacher carries out organizational, teaching and supervising functions. Functions of the pupil include acquaintance with a teaching material, the training which is necessary for formation of language skills and speaking skills, and application of investigated language in the solving of communicative problems.

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